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PROCESNE ULOGE DETETA U POSEBNIM PORODIČNIM PARNIČNIM POSTUPCIMA

Status deteta kao procesnog subjekta u savremenom procesnom pravu posebno je poboljšan na normativnom planu odredbama Porodičnog zakona (2004) usklađenog sa odredbama ratifikovane Konvencije o pravima deteta jer su mu, pored tradicionalnih, priznata i posebna procesna prava i garantovana njihova zaštita, bez obzira na to da li se prava deteta štite direktno ili indirektno. U parničnom postupku u kome se rešavaju nastali porodičnopravni sporovi dete može da se javi u različitim procesnim ulogama zavisno od vrste pravne zaštite koja se pruža po pravilima posebnih porodičnih parničnih postupaka. Dete može da se javi u ulozi parnične stranke, umešača i svedoka. S obzirom na to da su detetu priznata određena porodična prava, zakonodavac mu je priznao aktivnu procesnu legitimaciju da bi mu omogućio da ta prava zaštiti tako da ono ima procesni položaj aktivne stranke. Iako mu je priznao aktivnu procesnu legitimaciju, nije mu priznao istovremeno i procesnu sposobnost, te dete mora da bude zastupano na odgovarajući način, zavisno od konkretne situacije. Dete se javlja u pojedinim posebnim parničnim postupcima i kao nužna parnična stranka, u aktivnoj i pasivnoj stranačkoj ulozi i to kao aktivni ili pasivni suparničar zbog prirode porodičnopravnog odnosa.

Iako je dete subjekt određenih prava koja mu pripadaju, ono u nizu situacija predstavlja „pokrivenu stranku“ ili je objekt postupanja. Dete je pokrivena stranka u alimentacionoj parnici koju pokreće organ starateljstva kao stranka u funkcionalnom smislu u cilju određivanja visine doprinosa za izdržavanje ili u cilju promene visine doprinosa za izdržavanje ukoliko roditelj kao zastupnik deteta neopravdano ne pokrene postupak za ostvarenje prava deteta na izdržavanje odnosno povećanje doprinosa za izdržavanje. Dete je najčešće „pokrivena“ stranka u oficijelnim adhezionim postupcima koje po službenoj dužnosti pokreće sud u interesu deteta. Ti postupci su jednostranački i u njima su najčešće roditelji kao pasivni suparničari. Dete je objekt postupanja i kad je zakonom predviđeno da roditelji mogu da se sporazumeju u pogledu vršenja roditeljskog prava i kad sklapaju sporazum koji se tiče deteta a koji će biti podloga za sudsku odluku ukoliko sud oceni da je u interesu deteta.

Dete koje na poziv suda uzima učešće u parnici koja se vodi povodom porodičnopravnog spora nalazi se u ulozi specifičnog umešača sui generis. Ono se ne pridružuje ni jednom od roditelja kao parničara ni u parnici koja je pokrenuta tužbom, ni u oficijel-

nom adhezijom postupku pokrenutom u cilju zaštite prava i interesa deteta. Ovlašćenja deteta kao umešača sui generis proizlaze iz njegovog subjektiviteta i zakonom priznatog prava na participaciju u svim pravnim odnosima i pravnim stvarima koje se tiču njega i njegovih interesa i parnične stranke ne mogu da se protive njegovom učešću. Dete kao umešač sui generis može da preuzima samo zakonom određene parnične radnje i pod određenim uslovima i njihovo dejstvo parnične stranke ne mogu da anuliraju svojim parničnim radnjama. Dete može da bude saslušano kao stranka u sopstvenoj parnici, a kao učesnik u postupku u širem smislu može da bude saslušano u tuđoj parnici i kao svedok ali i kad je bilo umešač sui generis.

Ključne reči: posebni porodični parnični postupci, dete kao stranka, dete kao „prijavljena stranka“, dete kao objekt postupanja, dete kao umešač sui generis, dete kao svedok.

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PROCEDURAL ROLES OF THE CHILD IN SPECIAL FAMILY LITIGATION PROCEEDINGS

The status of the child as a procedural subject in the contemporary civil procedure law has been particularly strengthened at the normative level by the provisions of the Serbian Family Act (2004), which is harmonized with the provisions of the ratified UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. In addition to traditional rights, the child has been granted special procedural rights and guaranteed their protection, regardless of whether the child's rights are protected directly or indirectly. In civil proceedings for resolving family law disputes, the child may appear in different procedural roles, depending on the type of legal protection provided under the rules of special family litigation proceedings. The child may appear in the role of a party to the proceedings, an intervener, or a witness. Given the fact that certain family rights have been recognized to the child, the legislator has granted the child active procedural standing in order to enable the protection of those rights, thus giving the child the procedural position of an active party. Yet, although the child has been granted active procedural standing, the legislator has not recognized the child's procedural capacity; thus, the child must be represented in an appropriate manner, depending on the specific situation. In certain special litigation proceedings, the child may also appear as a necessary litigant, having both active and passive roles, acting either as an active or a passive co-litigant, depending on the nature of the family-law relationship.

Although the child is the subject of pertinent substantive and procedural rights, in many situations the child functions as a "hidden" party or as the object of proceedings. The child is a "hidden" party in alimony litigation initiated by the guardianship authority, which acts as a functional party for the purpose of determining the child support amount or modifying the child support amount if the parent, as the child's legal representative, unjustifiably fails to initiate proceedings for the realization of the child's right to maintenance or an increase in maintenance. The child is most often a "hidden" party in official adhesion proceedings that the court initiates ex officio in the best interest of the child. These proceedings are unilateral, and the parents typically appear as passive co-litigants. The child is also the object of the proceedings when the law provides that parents may reach an agreement concerning the exercise of parental rights, or when they conclude a child-related agreement that will serve as the

basis for the judicial decision, provided that the court determines that the agreement is in the child's best interests.

A child who, acting upon the court's invitation, takes part in a litigation concerning a family-law dispute assumes the role of a specific intervener *sui generis*. The child does not join a parent as a litigant, either in proceedings initiated by filing a complaint or in official adhesion proceedings initiated for the purpose of protecting the rights and interests of the child. The child's rights as an intervener *sui generis* arise from the child's status of a legal subject and the legally recognized right to participate in all legal relationships and legal matters that concern the child and his/her interests; thus, parties to the proceedings cannot oppose the child's participation. As an intervener *sui generis*, the child may undertake only those procedural actions that are specified by the law and only under certain conditions; the effects of such actions cannot be annulled by the procedural actions taken by the litigating parties. A child may be heard as a party in his/her own proceedings. As a participant in broader proceedings, the child may be heard in another person's litigation proceedings both as a witness and as an intervener *sui generis*.

Keywords: special family litigation proceedings, child as a party, child as a "hidden" party, child as the object of proceedings, child as an intervener *sui generis*, child as a witness.